

1. Paris
2. 1415
3. 4
4. The liver
5. Violets are blue
6. 13, 21, 34
7. Band of brothers"
8. Karl XII
9. Um
10. A.A Milne
11. 12472 km
12. Bond
13. Lolibobrorarory
14. London
- 15.

16. Asia
17. defeated Harold Godwinson at Hastings/ invaded England/ fought the battle of Hastings
18. 33
19. Inflammation
20. corner
21. pi
22. vici"
23. tsar Peter the Great
24. ist
25. Alice in Wonderland
26. Jupiter
27. stirred
28. Too Long; Didn't Read
29. Sankt Petersburg
- 30

31. Sweden
32. Constantinople
33. 21
34. The spinal cord
35. Moe
36. 162
37. so few
38. 1632
39. Window
40. Pippi Longstockings/70 languages
41. The Earth
42. problem"
43. ifteen-fay/ fifteen-fay
44. Rome
- 45.

46. The Alps
47. Pepin the Short
48. 46
49. The plague/the black death

50. fellow
51. 64
52. means."
53. field marshal
54. the indo-european language family
55. though he was only three
56. Saturn
57. you"
58. Waltz
59. Egypt/ Giza